

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B289
Date: 29 April 2007
Take Off: 14:33:56
Landing: 20:07:05
Flight Time: 5h33m09

Campaign: IASI – METOP and AQUA overpass

Operating Area: Oklahoma ARM site

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Foster	DFL
2	Co-pilot	Steve Ball	DFL
3	CCM	Sue Angold	DFL
4	Mission Scientist 1	Claire Lee	Met Office
5	Flight Manager	Ruth Purvis	FAAM
6	Cloud Physics	Paul James	FAAM
7	AVAPS / CCM2	Doug Anderson	FAAM
8	ARIES	Joss Kent	Met Office
9	MARSS / Wet Neph / PSAP	Dave Pollard	Met Office
10	AMS	Paul Williams	U of Manchester
11	CVI / FWVS	Jeff Brown	Met Office
12	Mission Scientist 2	Alessio Bozzo	U of Bologna
14	Neph	Dave Tiddeman	Met Office
15			
16			
17			
18			
19			
20			

Flight Track:

B289 Track 29-APR-07

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B289
 Date: 29/7/2007
 Project: IASI
 Location: Houston

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
142151		Start-Up	-.22 kft	179	29'36.28N 95'10.06W
143026		ASP	-.22 kft	000	open
143356		T/O	-.24 kft	179	
145253		Video	24.0 kft	141	UFC1 DFC1
153055	155714	Run 1	26.0 kft	120	
153133		Sonde 1	26.0 kft	175	
153959		Sonde 2	26.0 kft	186	
154302		Sonde 3	26.0 kft	186	
154600		Sonde 4	26.0 kft	185	
154800		Sonde 5	26.0 kft	187	
155000		Overpass	26.0 kft	186	METOP 1550Z
155400		Sonde 6	26.0 kft	186	
155439		Video	26.0 kft	186	RFC and FFC for final sonde 6 and 7
155634		Sonde 7	26.0 kft	186	
160241	162703	Run 1.2	26.0 kft	344	
160357		Sonde 8	26.0 kft	356	
160912		Sonde 9	26.0 kft	354	
161200		Sonde 10	26.0 kft	354	
161600		Sonde 11	26.0 kft	353	
162552		Video	26.0 kft	356	DFC2 UFC2
163327	165950	Profile 1	26.0 - 1.1 kft	191	baby run
165950	170305	Run 2.1	1.1 kft	177	at P end
170713	174317	Run 3.1	1.3 kft	005	1600ft
174643	181307	Profile 2	1.1 - 29.0 kft	178	1400ft N to S
181135		Video	27.7 kft	187	UFC3 DFC3
181307	181521	Run 4.1	29.0 kft	186	N to S
181940	184509	Run 4.2	29.0 kft	001	
182001		Sonde 12	29.0 kft	001	
182458		Sonde 13	29.0 kft	352	
183014		Sonde 14	29.0 kft	354	
183500		Sonde 15	29.0 kft	354	
183959		Sonde 16	29.0 kft	354	
184446		Sonde 17	29.0 kft	353	
185056	185718	Run 4.3	29.0 kft	191	N to S
185111		Sonde 18	29.0 kft	191	
185348		comment	29.0 kft	189	run 8 miles east
185701		Sonde 19	29.0 kft	190	
190122	190849	Run 4.4	29.0 kft	338	mid to N
190141		Sonde 20	29.0 kft	338	
190834		Sonde 21	29.0 kft	353	
191137	191152	Run 5	29.7 - 29.8 kft	304	
191211	194926	Run 5	30.0 kft	306	
191900		Overpass	30.0 kft	304	AQUA 1919Z
200705		Land	-.17 kft	177	
201034		Final	-.15 kft	179	29'36.28N 95'10.06W
201147		ASP	-.15 kft	179	

B289 Track 29-APR-07

Sortie Brief Eastern Gulf of Mexico

Flight B289

Sunday 29th April 2007

Mission Scientist: Clare Lee

Briefing: 0730L 1230Z

Take off: 0930L 1430Z

Final landing: approximately 1700L

Satellite overpasses 1550Z (MetOp) & 1919Z (AQUA)

Aim: To underfly IASI on the MetOp satellite and AIRS on AQUA, in the Gulf of Mexico just off the sub satellite tracks.

Location: Gulf of Mexico.

Weather conditions: Clear skies or broken clouds.

Key instruments: ARIES, MARSS, AVAPS, Core Chem, Cloud Phys

Fixed Points: BAe 146 to follow fixed ground positions as follows:

Fixed point "North": (27° 10' N, 90° 30' W)

Fixed point "South": (25° 00' N, 90°30' W)

	Time	Manoeuvre	Duration (mins)
1.	1430Z	Take off from Houston and transit to point "North", in position for SLR Southwards	60
2.	1530Z	SLR at FL260, from "North" to "South". Drop sondes starting at pt "North"	35
3.	1550Z	MetOp Overpass	
4.	1605Z	Reciprocal SLR from "South" to "North". Drop sondes	35
5.	1640Z	Profile descent from "North" to "South" to 1400ft, then continue on to "South"	30
6.	1710Z	SLR from "South" to "North" at 1400ft	50
7.	1800Z	Profile ascent from "North" to "South" from 1400ft to FL320 then continue on to "South" at FL320	35
8.	1835Z	SLR from "South" to "North" at FL300. Drop sondes	35
9.	1919Z	AQUA Overpass	
10	2000Z	Land Ellington	

Special notes for dropsonde launches: aim is to launch sondes with good coverage along the sub-satellite track but with particular density at the overpass time.

For MetOp overpass

Dropsonde	Time (Z)	Time relative to overpass (mins)
#1	1540	T-10
#2	1543	T-7
#3	1546	T-4
#4	1548	T-2
#5	1556	T+6
#6	1559	T+9
#7	1602	T+12

Reciprocal run

#8	1616
#9	1620
#10	1624
#11	1635

For AQUA overpass

#12	1845	
#13	1855	
#14	1903	
#15	1909	T-10
#16	1912	T-7
#17	1915	T-4
#18	1917	T-2

Mission scientist Debrief Summary
29th April 2007
JAIVEx Gulf of Mexico during MetOp and AQUA

Mission Scientist: Clare Lee

Weather Conditions:

For the majority of the science there was either low level Cu or StCu, with clear skies above. Small quantities of cirrus were observed at the start of the sortie in the area. Throughout the flight the atmosphere dried. The lower level Cu also reduced accordingly. Along the track the centre point had the largest cloud concentration and reduced towards either end to give some clear slots.

In the moister areas at high level the aircraft produced intermittent contrails (not recorded on the cameras, as UFC and DFC were recorded for most of the flight).

Sortie:

This flight was a successful validation sortie, coincident with 2 satellite overpasses and the WB57 aircraft (with NASI-I and S-HIS onboard). To sample the atmosphere close to both of the satellite times, 21 sondes were launched. Due to the location of the Northern point there was no advantage in refuelling at an alternative airport, compared to landing in Houston with its very close diversion.

The transit was made over the gulf to the Northern point. A run at high altitude (FL260) was flown towards the South point. During this run a dropsonde was launched at the North point, then 4 were launched just before the MetOp overpass time (1550Z), so that all 4 were at different altitudes in the atmosphere at the overpass. A 6th sonde was launched 6 minutes later, and a 7th at the South point. A slow turn was made, so that there was no loss in dropsonde transmission. On the reciprocal run 4 equally spaced dropsondes were launched.

A profile from North towards South was then made down to 1400ft (the minimum altitude allowed due to the error in the NOTAM submitted). A short run was flown to continue the leg to the South point. A low level run from South to North was made, however to be just above the Cu tops rather than in them for the benefit of the radiometers, it was flown at 1600ft.

A profile to FL290 (limited by air traffic) was made from North towards South, with a short run at FL290 to get to South point. During the reciprocal high level run sondes were dropped at regular intervals. At the North point, the fuel situation meant that only a short run to the South and back was possible before transit to Houston. A slow turn was made to avoid transmission losses again. To maximise time on task the Southern run was made slightly East and down wind of the original track, with a sonde launched at both ends of the run. A slow turn was made for the return leg North. Two more sondes were dropped in this run, the latter at point North (10 minutes before the AQUA satellite overpass time at 1919Z). A slow turn and ascent to FL300 were made for the transit to Houston. The transit leg was given a run number, with all instruments still in science mode.

Instrument Issues:

SWS: All OK

ARIES: All OK

MARSS: OK, except ch16

AVAPS: Some intermittent signal problems

Core: OK

Cloud Physics: OK

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.289** Date **29/4/07** Name **C. LEE** Page **1** of **8**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
~1430Z					T10 Ellington, Texas
143356	T10.				1/8 thin Ci local. + haze. Occasional Cu puff.
1444		FL140	089		layer ^{thin} of cloud ~ FL140 dry above. 5/8 Ci overhead
1452		FL240			Transit at at this level.
1510		FL240	121	28°06'N / 92°12'W	Hazy layer to S, no Ci Some, ~1/8 Ci to N.
1524		FL240	122		Climbing to FL260 ready for science. Cloud increasing - haze + patches of isolated Ci to East. Wind 12ms ⁻¹ / 277°
		FL260			Point N in clear sky, just haze.
153055	R1	FL260	175	27°06'N / 90°24'W	Run from N → S.
153130	D1	FL260		27°06'N / 90°24'W	Digsondel 1 launched. FATES maybe seeing Ci, MANSS seeing some moisture above.
153508		FL260	185		Care into moist region. - damp. increased. some contrails forming Some low level SW in Sallern region. DFC low contrast ⇒ moist below. T = -27.6°C, T _d = -27.5°C
153915		FL260		26°30'N / 90°30'W	Going over edges of SW - building as heading S.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B...B289** Date **29/4/07** Name **C. LEE** Page **2** of **8**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
153959	D2			26°24'N / 90°30'W	Dropsonde 2 launched.
1542					Drop 1 landed.
154302	D3	FL260		26°6'N / 90°30'W	Dropsonde 3. launched
154421					Can see contrail of WB57 ahead ~ 15 miles
					420 units over ground
					cf. 320 for Boelke.
	D3				418 SW below v. shallow.
154600	D4	FL260	185	25°54'N / 90°26'W	Dropsonde 4 launched.
					WB contrail not persistent - only ~ 2 miles behind.
154800	D5	FL260	187	25°42'N / 90°24'W	Dropsonde 5 launched.
1550					Altitudes of dropsondes at over pass (SPS in m) for 2, 3, 4, 5 : 294, 242, 4606, 6280 m
					Wind 20ms ⁻¹ / 266
1552					WB57 turning to East. (left turn)
155348					sonde 3 landed.
155400	D6	FL260	186	24°6'N / 90°24'W	Dropsonde 6.
155634	D7	FL260	186	24°34'N / 90°24'W	Dropsonde 7 Alt Sallern pt.
155714					Wind 20ms ⁻¹ / 268°.
155834	Rland	FL260	186		End run at point "South"
155730					Sonde 4 landed
155825					Sonde 5 landed.

some loss in 6+7 maybe due to too large banks in turn.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.289** Date **29/11/07** Name **CLEE** Page **3** of **8**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
160241	R1.2	FL260	357	25°06'N / 90°24'W	Reciprocal turn & Heading N to pt. "North".
160357	D8	FL260			dropsonde launched.
1604	D8				dropsonde 6 landed.
1607					dropsonde 7 landed.
160912	D9	FL260			Dropsonde launched.
161200	D10	FL260	354	25°48'N / 90°24'W	Dropsonde launched. wind 15ms ⁻¹ / 287° T -27°, T _D -38°C.
					Clear Clear above, air drying out at this altitude as heading N-NE below thinning to W.
					Sonde 9 having launch det. prob.
161600	D11	FL260	354	26°06'N / 90°24'W	Dropsonde launched.
161540					Sonde 8 landed. winds 16ms ⁻¹ / 284° T = -27.3°C, T _D = -36.5°C.
1617		FL260		26°24'N / 90°24'W	Coming into clear region some small turbulence.
1619					drop 9 landed.
1621					moist at this level, some conbrating visually no Ci, but insts. seeing moisture above.
1625					MARSS seeing more moisture at northern end than southern

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.289**..... Date **29/4/07**..... Name **C. LEE**..... Page **4** of **8**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					end, but now drier than start of R1-1
					T = -27.5°C, T _D -42.9°C.
162703	R1.2 end				end run. Slow bank to right (East).
162900					some I1 landed. Some wispy Ci in large banked ^{turn} area
163327	P1 ↓	F260	193	27° 51' N / 90° 30' W	Pt. Pt. N. Mth. As leading S. becoming hazier, no Ci, the + low level SW broken up from earlier ~ 3/8 w sly mistish layer at ~ F2150 + at F260 at pt. N.
1655					Bit mist at 500ft. (no cloud) still just 4/8 scattered w below. End profile
165950	P1	1400ft	177		Running towards "South"
165950	R2.1	1400ft.	177		Just in tops of w. w base ~ 1000ft. tops ~ 1500ft.
170305	R2.1 end				End run at "South", turning left. Run at slightly high alt to be above w tops.

Unfortunately can't go lower due to notam

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.289**..... Date 29/4/07 Name C. LEE..... Page 5 of 8

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
170713	R3	1600ft	001	2500'N / 90°30'W	Run from S → N. T = 24, T _D = 3.93 wind 4ms ⁻¹ / 126°
1709					Maybe touching w tops.
171050					In clear slot.
171146					In patchy w area ~ 4/8 Heimann surface ~ 28°C. similar to MARS.
171351					MARS 15WS zenith looks clear above.
~1717					into clear slot.
1818					small puffs, can see ^{lots of} see oil on sea surface.
172045					back into main w area
172119					In isolated clud., v. small water on ESSP
172145				
					In + at of clud tops.
172345					Out of main bulk of w. now just v. patchy + below aircraft alt.
				2600'N / 90°24'W	MARS seeing drier above at Northern end
172515					Clear slot. occasionally tiny w puff.
172730					Small w puffs ~ 1/8 clear above.

Mission Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B...289**.....

 Date **29/11/07**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
1738					Clear at as leading to Marken point.
174230				2700' N / 90° 32' W	Oil rig to right hand side lots of oil markings on sea surface
174317	R3	1600ft.		2706' N / 90° 26' W	End of run at pt. N. procedural turn.
174643	R2↑	1400ft.			Profile from 1400ft Very clear above + below. still hazy in disk.
174715	R2↑	1400ft.			Most at 1400 ft very dry.
175300		8000ft.			Drier layer. for < 1000ft.
175425		9700ft.			Moister layer : T=6, T _d =0.1°C
175550		11200ft.			Drying again. slightly only.
		11900ft.			main finding: T3, T _d -1.9. moisture.
1757		12700ft.			Drying. again.
1800					Over to area.
1802.		17800ft.		2606' N /	V. dry layer.
		FL220			moistering. but no contrail's
181307	P2end.	FL290			End run leading towards S.
	R4.1				Finishing run towards "S".
181521	R4.lead	FL290			PA point "S"
					T=-33, T _d -52
					Clear above, v. patchy to below. ~ 2/8.
181940	R4.2	FL290	002		Start run S → N

Mission Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B.289**.....

 Date **29/4/07**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
182001	D12	FL290			Drop sonde launched.
182458	D13	FL290	351		Drop sonde launched. wind 20ms ⁻¹ / 273° T = 33.4° → T _D = -51.5°C. clear above, 3/8 W below.
183003	D14	FL290	002	25°48'N / 90°24'W	Drop sonde launched. winds 20ms ⁻¹ / 271°
183120					Sonde 12 landed.
183500	D15	FL290	354		Drop sonde launched. clear above + below. MARCS seeing slight moistening 45 leading N.
1836					Sonde 13 landed. (can see WBS far in dist (00N) heading S. (slightly to E).
183959	D16	FL290	353	26°42'N / 90°24'W	Drop sonde launched. wind 19ms ⁻¹ / 295°.
184036					WB57 right overhead.
184120					Drop 14 landed.
184446	D17	FL290	354		Drop sonde launched. at pt. "N"
184509	R4-2and				End run at pt. N. sonde 15 landed. Very slow turn to right. rather next run will be offset to E. ~ 8 miles.

Mission Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B.289**.....

 Date **29/4/07**.....

 Page **8** of **8**.....

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
184056	R4-3	FL290			Run Leading S. (displaced).
185110	D18	FL290	190		Drop sonde launched.
185150					Sonde 16 landed.
1855					~ 17? ---
185701	D19	FL290	190	280°30' N / 90°12' W	Drop sonde launched.
					winds 18ms ⁻¹ / 278°
185718	R4-3 end	FL290			Run end. Slow turn to right ready for run to N.
190122	R4-4	FL290	338	26°26' N / 90°26' W	Run Leading North Clear above + below.
190156	D20	FL290			Sonde released.
1902					Sonde 18 landed.
1905					ARRIES claiming to Ci above - can't see visually.
190834	D21	FL290	354	27°01' N / 90°30' W	Drop sonde at point "North".
					winds: 16ms ⁻¹ / 292°
190849	R4-4 end	FL290			End run at "North"
					Have to head back to Ellington
191211	RS	FL 290 ³⁰⁰	305		calling this transit a run. Increased alt due to air traffic. ARRIES + SWS + MARSS still taking data.
191900		FL300	305	27°42' N / 91°12' W	Satellite overpass (AGUA) clear above - lower + middle dwd increasing in d3t. (Leading

194926 RS end. descent to Ellington towards NW).

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B289 **T/O:** 143356
Date of flight: 29/04/07 **Land:** 200705

A) FFSSP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Transfer *.txt files from DVD to processing PC Bnnn_FFSSP_hh.txt for each hour of data Bnnn_FFSSP_HVMS.txt	No	hh = Last sec processed =
2) FTP the files (ascii) from the PC to directory PMSDATA: on FLOODS		File size =
3) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP]FFSSP_EXTRACT_TAS a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Path name: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX c) Output directory: PMSDATA: d) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (see comment box)</i> e) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>		Use time just before/after take-off/landing. If T/O /landing just after/before the hour, ensure start/end time is before/after the hour if there is an FFSSP_hh.txt file for that hour.
4) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP]FFSSP_PROCESS_TXT a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) TAS in processing: Y d) Vel threshold (clicks) 0 e) Calibration file: <i>Use the most recent calibration file.</i> Format FFSSP_CALddmmyyyy.txt Calibration files to be stored in MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP] f) Adjust FFSSP time Y/N g) If Y, enter value to add to data time (seconds)		Total glitches = Sec file written ok? Note calibration file used Yes only if gross errors occur in FFSSP time eg; ~ 1hour
5) FLOODS> WAVE a) WAVE> write_procffssp_to_m5,'pmsdata:Bnnn_procffssp.dat', 'mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX','pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp',/auto b) WAVE> exit		Use PVWAVE for this section Note time correction applied to FFSSP by /auto =
6) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY (y=x+1) d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>		Input file size = M5 output file size =
7) CHECKS: i). Are FFSSP and JW/Nevzorov LWC synchronized in time? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>JW LWC para 535</i> <i>Nevzorov LWC para 602</i> <i>FFSSP LWC para 1202</i> ii). If not, repeat from step 5b replacing /auto with addt=x which adds x+20 secs to FFSSP time.		Synchronized?

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B289 **T/O:** 143356
Date of flight: 29/04/07 **Land:** 200705

B) 2D PROCESSING		REPROCESS +1hr
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Transfer Bnnn.dat file from CD/DVD to PC	Y	
2) Zip up file on PC (Bnnn.zip)	Y	
3) FTP the zipped file (binary) from the PC to the directory SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] on FLOODS	Y Y	
4) Log on to FLOODS	Y	
5) Unzip SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.zip	y	Size of Bnnn.dat = 194352
6) FLOODS> WAVE WAVE> CONVERT_SEADAS_FILE a) Input file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.dat b) Output file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn_seadas.dat WAVE> exit		Use PVWAVE for this section Blocks read = 48801 Blocks written = 48801 Bad reads =
7) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.SEADAS]READM200_FILE a) Default directory: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) Disk file name: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] Bnnn_seadas.dat d) Comment string: e) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O – 5 min)</i> f) End time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land + 5 min)</i> g) Read 2DC: Y h) Read 2DP: Y i) Secondary data: Y j) FSP-SYNC: Y k) cmd.str: Y l) Auto time correction: N m) Full length secondary: N	yes	Start = 143356 End = 200705 Ignore error message scroll (vestigial error from tapes) Are FRW, FSP, IMB, PCA,SEC files in PMSDATA? Are they non-zero in size? yes
8) FLOODS> WAVE i). WAVE> imagedisplay a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) Time from IWC plot: N d) Select probe: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP e) Start time: <i>As in 7e above</i> f) End time: <i>As in 7f above</i> g) Time interval (sec): 5 recommended (0 for all images) ii). WAVE> auto_image a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) Enter date: YYYYMMDD d) Enter start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O – 1 min)</i> e) Enter end time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land – 1 min)</i> f) Enter time interval (sec) between successive imaged blocks: 10 iii). WAVE> exit to create files iv). FTP ascii *.PS files from PMSDATA: to PC v). Load each into Ghostview or other pdf-converter vi). Output as pdf file (720 dpi resolution), appending name prefix of CORE-CLOUD-PHY_ to converted files	no	2D image display and printing Must be done from FLOODS itself. NO CLOUD NOISE ON BOTH PROBES Prepare imagery for Core data From own PC again Start = 143356 End = 200705 FAAM_YYYYMMDD_R0_ Bnnn_2Dx-images.ps Notes on this in instructions

<p>9) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.SPEC2D.AUTO]PROCESS2D_AUTO</p> <p>a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) File generation: <i>Hit enter</i> d) Time correction: <i>Time offset of the 2D data</i> e) TAS: Y f) MFD directory: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX g) Probe number: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP (0) Both <i>0 unless either probe known to be faulty</i> h) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O + 30sec)</i> i) End time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land – 30sec)</i> j) Nominal averaging: 0.2 seconds for conversion to M5 k) Particle type 2DC: 8 if known to be in ice cloud 11 if known to be in water cloud l) Particle type 2DP: 8 if known to be in mixed-phase 8 if unknown m) Coefficient choice: 2 n) Output root filename: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROC2D</p>	no	<p>NB. an error message may appear, floating point exception, rerun and use time quoted in error message, repeat until successful.</p> <p>X =</p> <p>Start = End =</p> <p>Time data processed to =</p> <p>2dproc files present? *.2dc, *.2dp and *.dat</p>
<p>10) FLOODS> WAVE</p> <p>i) WAVE> WRITE_PROC2D_TO_M5, 'PMSDATA:BNNN_PROC2D.DAT', 'PMSDATA:BNNN_M5PROC2D' ii). exit</p>	no	<p>Use PVWAVE for this section</p> <p>Error message about HDDR file should be ignored.</p> <p>Records =</p>
<p>11) FLOODS> MODIFY</p> <p>a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5proc2D b) Datset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default</p>	no	<p>X = Y = (X+1)</p>
<p>12) CHECKS:</p> <p>Are 2DC/2DP IWC of comparable magnitude and well-correlated with Nevzorov TWC? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Nevzerov TWC para 605</i> <i>2DC IWC para 1302</i> <i>2DP IWC para 1312</i></p>	no	<p>Correlated?</p>

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG**Flight number: B289****T/O: 143356****Date of flight: 29/04/07****Land: 200705**

C) PCASP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Complete stage 7) in 2D processing Ensures Bnnn_FSP.DAT containing raw PCASP data is written to directory PMSDATA:	yes	
2) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.PCASP]PROCPCASP_NEW a) Flight number: Bnnn b) File name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_FSP.DAT c) Root output name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP Produces PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.DAT (binary) PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.OUT (ascii) d) Minimum size channel: <i>default = 1</i> <i>If smallest size channel are known to be noisy the value of the highest noise free channel to be entered here</i> e) Calibration volume flow rate: <i>Use the most recent value. 1.8ccs⁻¹</i> <i>Calibration files to be stored in Exeter</i> <i>Entering zero gives default value = 1.0 cm³s⁻¹</i> f) Time correction: <i>Same value as used in 2D processing stage 9d</i> g) Start time: <i>0 if unknown</i> h) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>	yes	Min size =2 Vol flow rate = 0.8
3) FLOODS> WAVE	yes	Use PVWAVE for this section
i).WAVE> write_procpcasp_to_m5, 'pmsdata:Bnnn_procpcasp.dat', 'pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp' ii). WAVE> exit		
4) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>	yes	
5) CHECKS Are PCASP and NEPH peaks synchronous? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Neph total blue scatter</i> <i>PCASP conc para 1550</i>		Merged OK?

FAAM Dropsonde Flight Log

Flight No.	B289	Date	29 Apr 2007
Page No.	1 of 2	Operator	Doug Anderson

GMT	Sonde No.	Event	Comments
		<i>e.g. launch, splashdown</i>	<i>e.g. wind data? PTH data? Lat/Long NB strings of dropsonde data contain: time, pressure hPa, T deg C, RH %, wind direction deg, wind speed m/s, longitude, latitude, height m</i>
			Sondes 1-11 launched around the 1630Z MetOp satellite overpass
15:31:36	1	Launch	359.40 -27.40 26.53 271.10 17.00 -18.80 - 90.482400 27.165200 7933.10
15:41:35	1	splashdown	1021.49 23.20 999.00 41.66 5.28 -8.49 - 90.467365 27.151914 99999.00 Weak telemetry between 19000' - 13000'. Better but still with occasional dropouts below 13000'.
15:40:03	2	Launch	359.40 -27.30 60.06 265.60 18.80 -18.00 - 90.500900 26.449700 7933.30
15:50:23	2	splashdown	1021.97 23.21 86.05 34.20 5.75 -3.61 - 90.487203 26.440496 99999.00
15:43:03	3	Launch	359.20 -27.20 54.52 263.00 20.90 -17.30 - 90.500600 26.189300 7937.00
15:53:34	3	splashdown	1021.69 23.30 86.09 80.94 4.83 -10.58 - 90.486258 26.178122 99999.00
154603	4	Launch	359.50 -27.20 96.38 268.70 19.90 -17.70 - 90.500500 25.927300 7932.00
155621	4	splashdown	1021.49 23.37 84.57 74.75 5.20 -9.31 - 90.483412 25.919287 99999.00
154803	5	Launch	359.50 -26.70 72.89 272.20 20.90 -17.80 - 90.500500 25.751500 7931.50
155810	5	splashdown	1021.74 23.50 85.78 56.22 6.12 -6.80 - 90.481942 25.741865 99999.00
155403	6	Launch	359.60 -25.50 16.93 269.30 20.20 -17.60 - 90.500500 25.222200 7930.90
160414	6	splashdown	1021.15 23.92 86.99 63.47 6.28 -11.39 - 90.485080 25.214303 99999.00 Weak telemetry as aircraft turned (drop between 11000 and 6000' and better
155639	7	Launch	359.40 -26.00 17.71 268.20 21.00 -17.50 - 90.498500 24.993000 7933.30
160653	7	splashdown	1020.94 24.25 87.73 59.64 6.22 -11.79 - 90.482955 24.986901 99999.00 Weak telemetry as aircraft turned (drop between 16000 and 11000'
160400	8	Launch	359.60 -25.40 14.41 278.40 17.90 -18.90 - 90.498900 25.209300 7930.90
161427	8	splashdown	1021.42 23.85 89.34 47.58 8.48 -2.76 - 90.482279 25.198956 99999.00 Intermittent GPS at times
160915	9	Launch	352.86 12.65 3.62 178.98 102.57 0.00 - 90.500052 25.653167 8577.91 NO Launch detect so not P00 value used
161908	9	splashdown	1020.93 23.44 84.43 77.89 5.36 -11.43 - 90.484439 25.644359 99999.00 NO Launch detect so not processed in Aspen
161203	10	Launch	359.60 -27.00 32.80 285.40 16.10 -17.40 - 90.500000 25.899600 7930.90
162221	10	splashdown	1021.52 23.55 84.01 64.30 4.99 -10.98 - 90.482698 25.887203 99999.00

Flight No.	B289	Date	29 Apr 2007
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GMT	Sonde No.	Event	Comments
		<i>e.g. launch, splashdown</i>	<i>e.g. wind data? PTH data? Lat/Long NB strings of dropsonde data contain: time, pressure hPa, T deg C, RH %, wind direction deg, wind speed m/s, longitude, latitude, height m</i>
161603	11	Launch	359.40 -27.30 40.47 284.50 16.80 -16.60 - 90.500000 26.253800 7934.00
162857	11	splashdown	1022.02 23.40 85.56 77.02 4.72 -8.89 - 90.483902 26.237276 99999.00 occ GPS dropouts for most of fall
			Sondes 12-21 launched around the 1934Z AQUA satellite overpass
182003	12	Launch	314.40 -33.20 15.43 266.80 21.40 -15.40 - 90.516500 24.888200 8849.10
183109	12	splashdown	1019.46 24.20 84.50 59.07 7.05 -11.28 - 90.488508 24.876852 99999.00 Occ drop out of GPS signal for most of drop
182503	13	Launch	314.70 -33.50 14.48 273.40 20.90 -15.60 - 90.497100 25.360700 8841.60
183555	13	splashdown	1019.90 23.48 84.25 66.47 5.96 -11.51 - 90.470421 25.347806 99999.00
183003	14	Launch	314.60 -33.70 16.02 271.10 21.10 -16.50 - 90.498200 25.816900 8844.10
184113	14	splashdown	1020.64 23.37 83.76 72.33 5.96 -11.35 - 90.473756 25.804222 99999.00
183503	15	Launch	314.40 -34.60 17.70 274.40 20.70 -16.20 - 90.499800 26.273100 8849.10
184610	15	splashdown	1021.07 23.13 85.29 59.60 5.58 -11.59 - 90.474899 26.257711 99999.00 some gps drop outs
184015	16	Launch	314.50 -35.30 26.41 300.00 20.50 -15.40 - 90.500400 26.752900 8846.50
185100	16	splashdown	1021.04 24.01 72.23 65.50 4.63 -11.35 - 90.478882 26.717716 99999.00
184448	17	Launch	314.50 -35.70 24.83 307.20 20.70 -15.10 - 90.499000 27.168600 8845.30
185545	17	splashdown	1020.31 23.60 78.62 43.49 4.07 -11.50 - 90.472919 27.153128 99999.00
185109	18	Launch	314.50 -35.70 60.65 293.50 18.10 -15.50 - 90.189200 27.053000 8845.30
190206	18	splashdown	1021.20 23.95 72.29 46.92 7.01 -2.24 - 90.162617 27.033965 99999.00
185703	19	Launch	314.50 -35.20 28.61 277.60 18.00 -15.00 - 90.222200 26.506300 8845.20
190753	19	splashdown	1020.30 23.74 77.21 62.39 4.90 -11.90 - 90.197843 26.490458 99999.00
190142	20	Launch	314.50 -35.20 28.29 293.40 17.10 -14.50 - 90.480100 26.533300 8845.40
191255	20	splashdown	9999.00 99.00 999.00 67.80 4.78 -11.14 - 90.455536 26.517862 99999.00 some GPS dropouts
191012	21	Launch	314.60 -35.80 21.37 279.80 19.90 -14.70 - 90.547800 27.300400 8843.00
191824	21	splashdown	9999.00 99.00 999.00 52.98 4.77 -12.06 - 90.479385 27.156342 99999.00

B289 CVI log

4/29/07	2:53:35 PM	zero	24kft
4/29/07	3:29:09 PM	zero	26kft
4/29/07	3:42:40 PM	zero	26kft
4/29/07	4:08:25 PM	zero	26kft
4/29/07	4:52:20 PM	zero	26kft
4/29/07	4:52:35 PM	zero	9kft
4/29/07	6:13:00 PM	zero	29kft
4/29/07	7:10:13 PM	zero	29kft

B289_SWS_SHIMS_EventLog.txt

```

13:13:07.25 --- - - - -
13:13:07.25 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
13:13:07.25 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
                    tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
13:13:07.25 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. B289
13:13:07.25 --- - - - -
13:14:13.39 SWS - - - - Initialising: VIS OK NIR OK
13:14:29.57 USH - - - - Initialising: VIS OK NIR OK
13:14:39.24 LSH - - - - Initialising: VIS OK NIR OK
13:15:03.97 SWS - - 500 - VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 500ms.
13:15:07.76 SWS - - - 500 NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 500ms.
13:15:11.07 USH - - 750 - VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 750ms.
13:15:14.61 USH - - - 750 NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 750ms.
13:15:17.39 LSH - - 750 - VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 750ms.
13:15:22.23 LSH - - - 750 NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 750ms.
13:15:27.35 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
13:15:36.73 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
13:15:42.10 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:15:42.10 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:15:42.12 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:15:48.52 SWS - - - - Idling
13:15:50.28 USH - - - - Idling
13:15:50.54 LSH - - - - Idling
13:15:54.57 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:15:54.57 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:15:54.58 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:16:00.19 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:16:00.39 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:16:00.43 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:16:06.03 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:16:08.13 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:16:08.34 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:16:19.14 SWS - - 750 - VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 750ms.
13:16:22.69 SWS - - - 750 NIR int.time changed from 500ms to 750ms.
13:16:25.21 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:16:29.07 USH - - 500 - VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 500ms.
13:16:33.46 USH - - - 990 NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 990ms.
13:16:34.13 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:16:36.44 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:16:46.77 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:16:52.98 LSH - - 990 - VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 990ms.
13:16:56.63 LSH - - - 990 NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 990ms.
13:16:58.38 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:16:58.59 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:16:58.60 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:17:06.31 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:17:08.94 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:17:09.14 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:18:18.39 SWS - - 500 - VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 500ms.
14:18:23.71 USH - - 250 - VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 250ms.
14:18:28.44 USH - - 150 - VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 150ms.
14:18:35.74 USH - - - 750 NIR int.time changed from 990ms to 750ms.
14:18:39.10 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
14:18:39.50 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
14:18:39.82 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
14:18:47.03 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:18:47.44 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:18:50.14 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:19:07.39 --- - - - - *** sws head aft for take off
14:21:10.12 --- - - - - *** peltiers 1&2 did not appear to work
                    initially
14:21:32.96 --- - - - - *** however now working OK. All pop switches
                    checked
14:21:40.34 --- - - - - *** as in
14:46:04.60 SWS 174R - - - - Telescope position set to 174R
14:46:33.14 --- - - - - *** in anticipation of first run
14:48:41.79 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.

```

14:48:41.82	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:48:41.89	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:48:49.73	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:48:49.93	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:48:52.55	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:57:24.98	SWS	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 400ms.
14:57:29.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:57:29.42	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:57:29.73	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:57:37.12	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:57:37.38	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:57:40.07	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:00:37.44	LSH	-	-	750	-	VIS int.time changed from 990ms to 750ms.
15:00:43.76	LSH	-	-	500	-	VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 500ms.
15:00:48.15	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:00:58.50	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:05:38.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:05:39.32	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:05:39.42	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:05:46.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:05:47.46	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:05:49.66	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:11:47.18	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:11:47.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:11:47.46	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:11:55.14	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:11:55.37	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:11:57.93	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:16:41.41	USH	-	-	-	500	NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 500ms.
15:16:44.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:16:44.80	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:16:44.98	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:16:50.55	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:16:52.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:16:55.24	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:22:14.23	USH	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 100ms.
15:22:17.44	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:22:17.54	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:22:17.61	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:22:22.87	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:22:25.59	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:22:28.17	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:27:21.83	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
15:27:29.04	SWS	-	-	500	-	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 500ms.
15:27:33.42	SWS	-	-	750	-	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 750ms.
15:27:38.22	SWS	-	-	500	-	VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 500ms.
15:27:41.95	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:27:41.99	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:27:42.46	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:27:47.58	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:27:49.89	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:27:52.80	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:31:08.41	---	-	-	-	-	*** start of run 1.0
15:31:17.04	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:31:17.26	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:31:17.62	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:31:22.51	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:31:25.20	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:31:27.96	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:31:32.66	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
15:31:37.92	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
15:31:43.98	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
15:32:03.29	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:32:15.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Instrument closed.
15:32:31.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Initialising: VIS OK NIR OK
15:32:33.72	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:32:49.85	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:32:50.12	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:32:50.59	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

15:32:55.56	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:32:58.57	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:33:00.94	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:34:55.85	SWS	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 400ms.
15:35:01.56	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
15:35:08.62	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:35:08.75	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:35:08.83	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:35:14.07	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:35:16.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:35:19.17	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:38:47.73	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:38:48.15	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:38:48.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:38:53.17	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:38:56.30	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:38:58.45	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:39:16.84	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
15:39:24.51	SWS	-	-	500	-	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 500ms.
15:39:28.38	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:39:28.43	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:39:29.05	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:39:34.02	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:39:36.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:39:39.39	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:40:39.12	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
15:40:44.54	SWS	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 400ms.
15:40:48.76	SWS	-	-	350	-	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 350ms.
15:40:55.82	SWS	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 300ms.
15:41:01.33	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:41:01.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:41:01.83	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:41:06.77	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:41:09.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:41:12.17	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:41:56.68	SWS	-	-	250	-	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 250ms.
15:42:02.37	SWS	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 200ms.
15:42:05.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:42:12.99	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:42:31.47	LSH	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 400ms.
15:42:34.80	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:42:45.13	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:45:29.71	---	-	-	-	-	*** above 5/8 cul
15:45:43.42	---	-	-	-	-	*** no ci above
15:46:04.40	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:46:04.69	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:46:04.90	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:46:10.16	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:46:12.35	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:46:15.24	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:47:14.70	SWS	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 300ms.
15:47:19.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:47:27.21	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:49:02.34	SWS	-	-	250	-	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 250ms.
15:49:04.26	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:49:12.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:49:36.19	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:49:36.23	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:49:36.37	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:49:42.43	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:49:43.16	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:49:44.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:49:46.60	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:50:01.48	---	-	-	-	-	*** metop overpass
15:56:38.12	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:56:38.28	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:56:38.47	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:56:43.76	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:56:46.45	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

15:56:48.47	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:57:32.82	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run 1.1
15:57:43.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:57:44.12	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:57:44.39	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:57:49.55	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:57:51.81	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:57:54.74	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:02:50.39	---	-	-	-	-	*** start of run 1.2
16:03:00.87	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:03:01.04	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:03:01.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:03:06.54	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:03:09.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:03:11.21	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:05:15.26	---	-	-	-	-	*** still over patches of cul
16:08:13.86	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:08:14.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:08:14.30	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:08:19.30	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:08:21.99	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:08:24.64	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:14:10.82	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:14:10.97	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:14:11.29	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:14:16.46	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:14:18.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:14:21.63	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:19:12.56	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:19:12.74	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:19:12.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:19:18.40	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:19:20.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:19:22.92	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:19:36.24	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
16:19:47.59	SWS	-	-	350	-	VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 350ms.
16:19:52.07	SWS	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 400ms.
16:19:56.95	SWS	-	-	500	-	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 500ms.
16:20:00.61	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:20:00.85	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:20:01.06	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:20:06.29	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:20:09.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:20:10.95	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:22:03.68	LSH	-	-	500	-	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 500ms.
16:22:08.94	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:22:19.28	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:23:36.62	SWS	-	-	350	-	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 350ms.
16:23:42.10	SWS	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 300ms.
16:23:46.91	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
16:23:51.12	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:23:51.60	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:23:51.69	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:23:56.56	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:23:59.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:24:02.10	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:27:13.36	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
16:27:17.62	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:27:17.66	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:27:17.85	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:27:23.08	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:27:25.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:27:28.37	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:36:02.77	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:36:03.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:36:03.19	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:36:08.24	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:36:11.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:36:13.72	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

16:37:43.77	---	-	-	-	*** currently in profile 1
16:41:15.52	USH	-	-	75	- VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 75ms.
16:41:19.66	USH	-	-	-	400 NIR int.time changed from 500ms to 400ms.
16:41:34.35	LSH	-	-	990	- VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 990ms.
16:41:39.61	USH	-	-	-	- Dark measurement started.
16:41:39.93	SWS	-	-	-	- Dark measurement started.
16:41:40.36	LSH	-	-	-	- Dark measurement started.
16:41:44.05	USH	-	-	-	- Manual scene recording started.
16:41:47.87	SWS	-	-	-	- Manual scene recording started.
16:41:50.70	LSH	-	-	-	- Manual scene recording started.
16:46:27.90	SWS	-	-	-	- Dark measurement started.
16:46:28.40	USH	-	-	-	- Dark measurement started.
16:46:28.47	LSH	-	-	-	- Dark measurement started.
16:46:32.84	USH	-	-	-	- Manual scene recording started.
16:46:35.84	SWS	-	-	-	- Manual scene recording started.
16:46:38.95	LSH	-	-	-	- Manual scene recording started.
16:52:46.10	USH	-	-	-	- Dark measurement started.
16:52:46.34	SWS	-	-	-	- Dark measurement started.
16:52:46.89	LSH	-	-	-	- Dark measurement started.
16:52:50.55	USH	-	-	-	- Manual scene recording started.
16:52:54.28	SWS	-	-	-	- Manual scene recording started.
16:52:57.23	LSH	-	-	-	- Manual scene recording started.
16:58:30.77	SWS	6F	-	-	- Telescope position set to 6F
16:58:38.73	SWS	-	-	100	- VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 100ms.
16:58:44.34	SWS	-	-	50	- VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 50ms.
16:58:51.37	SWS	-	-	-	- Dark measurement started.
16:58:51.46	USH	-	-	-	- Dark measurement started.
16:58:52.00	LSH	-	-	-	- Dark measurement started.
16:58:56.02	USH	-	-	-	- Manual scene recording started.
16:59:00.05	SWS	-	-	-	- Manual scene recording started.
16:59:01.03	SWS	-	-	-	- Manual scene recording started.
16:59:02.28	LSH	-	-	-	- Manual scene recording started.
17:00:10.53	---	-	-	-	*** start of run 2.1
17:00:20.24	SWS	-	-	75	- VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 75ms.
17:00:29.60	SWS	-	-	-	- Dark measurement started.
17:00:37.54	SWS	-	-	-	- Manual scene recording started.
17:02:28.23	---	-	-	-	*** 200ft climb during run
17:03:10.81	---	-	-	-	*** end of run
17:03:35.59	SWS	174R	-	-	- Telescope position set to 174R
17:03:51.20	SWS	-	-	300	- VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 300ms.
17:07:15.55	---	-	-	-	*** start of run 3
17:10:04.42	---	-	-	-	*** just above/in layer of cul
17:11:32.80	SWS	-	-	250	- VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 250ms.
17:11:36.22	SWS	-	-	-	- Dark measurement started.
17:11:44.16	SWS	-	-	-	- Manual scene recording started.
17:12:25.88	LSH	-	-	-	- Dark measurement started.
17:12:25.96	USH	-	-	-	- Dark measurement started.
17:12:26.11	SWS	-	-	-	- Dark measurement started.
17:12:30.58	USH	-	-	-	- Manual scene recording started.
17:12:34.22	SWS	-	-	-	- Manual scene recording started.
17:12:36.22	LSH	-	-	-	- Manual scene recording started.
17:14:00.83	SWS	6F	-	-	- Telescope position set to 6F
17:14:05.01	SWS	-	-	50	- VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 50ms.
17:14:20.29	LSH	-	-	750	- VIS int.time changed from 990ms to 750ms.
17:14:22.69	USH	-	-	-	- Dark measurement started.
17:14:22.87	SWS	-	-	-	- Dark measurement started.
17:14:23.00	LSH	-	-	-	- Dark measurement started.
17:14:27.12	USH	-	-	-	- Manual scene recording started.
17:14:30.82	SWS	-	-	-	- Manual scene recording started.
17:14:33.42	LSH	-	-	-	- Manual scene recording started.
17:15:36.18	SWS	174R	-	-	- Telescope position set to 174R
17:15:40.28	SWS	-	-	300	- VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 300ms.
17:15:44.92	SWS	-	-	250	- VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 250ms.
17:15:51.79	LSH	-	-	-	- Dark measurement started.
17:15:51.92	SWS	-	-	-	- Dark measurement started.
17:15:52.08	USH	-	-	-	- Dark measurement started.
17:15:56.64	USH	-	-	-	- Manual scene recording started.
17:15:59.94	SWS	-	-	-	- Manual scene recording started.
17:16:02.14	LSH	-	-	-	- Manual scene recording started.

17:16:29.12	---	-	-	-	*** having to use tape to hold 174 aft postition
17:20:13.88	SWS	6F	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
17:20:23.19	SWS	-	-	150	VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 150ms.
17:20:27.70	SWS	-	-	75	VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 75ms.
17:20:32.63	SWS	-	-	50	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 50ms.
17:20:36.78	USH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:20:36.84	LSH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:20:36.91	SWS	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:20:41.22	USH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:20:45.12	SWS	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:20:47.33	LSH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:21:53.47	SWS	174R	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
17:21:59.92	SWS	-	-	350	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 350ms.
17:22:27.72	SWS	-	-	300	VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 300ms.
17:22:34.78	SWS	-	-	250	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 250ms.
17:22:36.63	SWS	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:22:39.13	LSH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:22:39.26	USH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:22:43.77	USH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:22:44.58	SWS	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:22:49.47	LSH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:23:16.22	SWS	-	-	200	VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 200ms.
17:23:24.44	SWS	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:23:32.39	SWS	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:28:11.49	USH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:28:11.65	SWS	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:28:11.81	LSH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:28:15.98	USH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:28:19.67	SWS	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:28:22.26	LSH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:33:01.94	USH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:33:02.03	LSH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:33:02.06	SWS	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:33:02.61	USH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:33:07.10	USH	-	-	-	Idling
17:33:10.28	SWS	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:33:12.49	LSH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:43:25.88	USH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:43:26.55	LSH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:43:26.58	SWS	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:43:30.32	USH	-	-	-	Idling
17:43:33.17	---	-	-	-	*** end of run 3.1
17:43:34.70	SWS	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:43:36.89	LSH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:05:31.51	SWS	-	-	150	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 150ms.
18:05:36.76	LSH	-	-	400	VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 400ms.
18:05:42.47	USH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:05:42.99	SWS	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:05:43.23	LSH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:05:46.92	USH	-	-	-	Idling
18:05:50.93	SWS	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:05:53.57	LSH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:08:28.83	USH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:10:48.17	USH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:10:48.54	LSH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:10:48.76	SWS	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:10:52.61	USH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:10:56.70	SWS	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:10:58.89	LSH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:13:08.54	---	-	-	-	*** start of mini run
18:13:11.47	USH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:13:11.81	LSH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:13:12.22	SWS	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:13:15.92	USH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:13:20.17	SWS	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:13:22.16	LSH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:13:42.84	USH	-	-	350	NIR int.time changed from 400ms to 350ms.
18:13:47.27	USH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

18:13:51.21	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:14:22.48	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
18:14:27.71	SWS	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 50ms.
18:14:31.68	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:14:39.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:15:29.49	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
18:15:35.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:15:35.56	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:15:36.07	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:15:39.63	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:15:43.43	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:15:46.40	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:16:39.63	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
18:16:49.96	---	-	-	-	-	*** for start of next run
18:16:55.89	SWS	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 200ms.
18:17:05.28	SWS	-	-	250	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 250ms.
18:17:08.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:17:16.35	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:19:54.70	---	-	-	-	-	*** start of run
18:19:59.04	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
18:20:05.58	SWS	-	-	150	-	VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 150ms.
18:20:09.82	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:20:09.97	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:20:10.16	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:20:13.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:20:17.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:20:20.56	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:23:43.60	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
18:23:49.59	SWS	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 75ms.
18:23:54.98	SWS	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 50ms.
18:23:58.03	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:23:58.16	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:23:58.55	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:24:01.97	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:24:06.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:24:08.89	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:26:50.75	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
18:26:58.45	SWS	-	-	250	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 250ms.
18:27:04.00	SWS	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 200ms.
18:27:08.96	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:27:09.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:27:09.47	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:27:12.90	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:27:17.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:27:19.84	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:27:28.84	SWS	-	-	150	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 150ms.
18:27:31.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:27:39.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:31:39.37	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:31:39.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:31:39.53	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:31:43.33	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:31:47.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:31:48.24	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
18:31:50.12	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:31:52.97	SWS	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 75ms.
18:32:01.10	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:32:09.03	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:34:27.41	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
18:34:31.85	SWS	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 300ms.
18:34:37.33	SWS	-	-	250	-	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 250ms.
18:34:42.45	SWS	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 200ms.
18:34:46.68	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:34:46.69	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:34:46.89	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:34:51.03	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:34:55.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:34:57.25	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:36:05.15	LSH	-	-	500	-	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 500ms.

18:36:09.62	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:36:19.95	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:37:29.66	SWS	-	-	150	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 150ms.
18:37:33.29	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:37:41.22	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:40:05.06	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:40:05.15	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:40:05.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:40:08.99	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:40:13.40	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:40:15.60	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:45:14.66	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:45:14.71	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:45:15.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:45:18.80	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:45:23.09	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:45:25.00	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:50:23.80	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
18:50:30.58	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 100ms.
18:50:34.65	SWS	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 200ms.
18:50:41.43	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:50:41.54	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:50:41.81	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:50:45.77	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:50:49.57	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:50:51.77	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:53:53.00	---	-	-	-	-	*** run 4.3 started at 185056 offset east 8miles
18:56:46.44	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:56:46.52	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:56:47.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:56:50.39	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:56:54.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:56:57.09	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:57:24.93	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
19:00:03.44	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
19:00:07.25	SWS	-	-	150	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 150ms.
19:00:13.91	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:00:14.02	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:00:14.12	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:00:18.26	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:00:22.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:00:24.28	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:01:29.04	---	-	-	-	-	*** start of run 4.4
19:01:36.62	SWS	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 200ms.
19:01:40.66	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:01:48.56	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:01:48.60	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:01:50.74	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:01:52.51	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:02:01.07	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:04:12.74	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
19:04:25.13	SWS	-	-	150	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 150ms.
19:04:30.23	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:04:30.32	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:04:30.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:04:34.36	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:04:38.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:04:40.56	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:08:37.89	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
19:08:42.92	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:08:43.10	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:08:43.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:08:47.06	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:08:51.29	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:08:53.35	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:11:28.73	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
19:11:36.95	SWS	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 200ms.
19:11:52.58	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

19:11:52.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:11:52.84	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:11:56.53	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:12:00.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:12:03.31	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:12:20.74	---	-	-	-	-	*** start of run5
19:16:07.93	SWS	-	-	250	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 250ms.
19:16:12.41	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:16:12.73	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:16:12.75	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:16:16.68	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:16:20.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:16:23.30	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:19:08.49	---	-	-	-	-	*** aqua overpass
19:21:18.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:21:18.21	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:21:18.33	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:21:22.31	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:21:26.16	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:21:29.93	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:21:31.17	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:29:00.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:29:00.97	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:29:01.16	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:29:04.73	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:29:08.93	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:29:11.53	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:31:33.12	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
19:31:40.94	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:31:41.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:31:41.78	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:31:44.87	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:31:49.40	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:31:52.12	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:35:49.93	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:35:50.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:35:50.36	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:35:53.87	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:35:58.06	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:36:00.70	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:37:47.49	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of science for sws
19:38:28.26	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
19:38:30.52	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
19:38:32.89	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
19:38:57.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Instrument closed.
19:38:59.84	USH	-	-	-	-	Instrument closed.
19:39:01.40	LSH	-	-	-	-	Instrument closed.

ARIES flight log

Flight: 13289 page 1 of

Date: 29/04/07 Operator(s): Jess Res: 1 Gain A: ZB:Z

Loc./Notes: 1st HOUSTON W. Golf of Mexico

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
145500	Transit	1/60	CW	clsd	7028	32.81	FL240
145626	u u	600/1	Zen	open	7031	33.0	Nice cirrus above FL240
150150	u u	1/60	CW	clsd	?	?	FL240
1503	u u	600/1	Zen	open	7023	22.6	Cirrus above. FL240
150808	u u	1/60	CW	clsd	702	22.6	
150850	- error			unable			to get command confirmation
150937	u u	1/60	CW	clsd			
151051	u u	120/1	Nad	clsd	709	22.5	
153023	Run 1.1	1/60	CW	clsd	707	30.1	
153141	Run 1.1	300/1	Zen	open	703	31.4	Shows cirrus above
153422	u u	300/1	Nad	clsd	707	31.0	
153724	u u	1/60	CW	clsd	706	30.7	
153905	u u	120/1	Zen	open	702	30.9	
154016	u u	480/1	Nad	clsd	7075	30.37	St Cir below @ 300k, surface @ 302.2k
154437	u u	1/60	CW	clsd	7032	30.47	
154606	u u	600/1	Nad	clsd	7067	30.70	
155134	u u	1/60	CW	clsd	7072	31.21	
155357	u u	600/1	Nad	clsd	7077	30.71	ended 155735
155749	end Run 1.1	1/60	CW	clsd	7066	30.42	
160056		1/60	CW	clsd	7031	30.70	
160237		1/60	CW	clsd	7059	30.56	
160353	Run 1.2	600/1	Nad	clsd	7063	30.32	
160907	u u	1/60	CW	clsd	7067	30.38	
161025	u u	600/1	Nad	clsd	7068	30.71	
161525	u u	1/60	CW	clsd	7076	30.56	
161720	u u	480	Nad	clsd	7069	30.40	Stopped 162025
162032	u u	120	Zen	open	7009	30.63	- cal in between
162305	u u	300	Zen	clsd	7020	30.39	
162544	u u	300	Nad	clsd	7043	30.72	stopped @ 162707
162714	u u	1/60	CW	clsd	7051	30.56	cal script
163622	P1						Proble Zen not work

ARIES flight log

Flight:

B2.89

page 2 of

Date: 29/04/07

Operator(s): JGS

Res: 1

Gain A: 2 B:

Loc./Notes:

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
167720		Opened	Shutter?				for profile caps!
165946	API	1/60	Cal dso		709	30.07	
170101	R2.1	600/1	Zen open		709	31.6	ended 170305
170332	" "	1/60	Cal dso		709	32.3	
170607		1/60	Cal dso		709	31.82	
170725	R3.1	600/1	Nod dso		711	31.78	just above fluffy Cu
171224	" "	1/60	Cal dso		708	31.81	
171345	" "	120/1	Zen open		709	31.28	
171456	" "	480/1	Nod dso		709	32.06	
171900	" "	1/60	Cal dso		709	31.85	
172015	" "	120/1	Zen open		709	32.58	
172130	" "	480/1	Nod dso		712	33.05	
172532	" "	Cal 1/60	Cal dso		709	33.11	
172644	" "	600/1	Nod dso		709	33.00	
173149	" "	Cal 1/60	Cal dso		709	32.89	
173311	" "	600/1	Nod dso		709	33.38	
173420	" "	Cal 1/60	Cal dso		709	33.99	
173939	" "	600/1	Nod dso		710	33.39	end 174335
174343	" "	Cal 1/60	Cal dso		709	34.09	
174643	P2		Shutter				Profile ZHCNCHZx3
181303	one/2	Cal 1/60	Cal dso		698	31.6	
181423		120/1	Zen open		703	30.6	
181821	Swire 14.1	Cal 1/60	Cal dso		707	30.91	
181904	14.1	300/1	Nod dso		707	31.21	
182335	RL4.1	300/1	Zen open		707	30.76	
182606	" "	Cal 1/60	Cal dso		707	30.91	
182725	" "	480/1	Nod dso		707	30.20	
183135	" "	120/1	Zen open		707	31.25	
183250	" "	Cal 1/60	Cal dso		707	30.63	
184420	" "	600/1	Nod dso		707	30.9	

ARIES flight log

Flight: B289 page 3 of

Date: 29/04/07 Operator(s): Joss Res: 1 Gain A: 2 B: 2

Loc./Notes:

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
183924	R4-1	1/60	cal	clsd	7072	3052	
184050	u u	520	Nod	clsd	7045	3060	— stalled. resumed Acquisition
184204	u u	520	u	u	7072	3058	ended @ 184512
184532	end u	1/60	cal	clsd	7072	3124	Cal
184930	Scans R5	1/60	cal	clsd	7071	3058	
185104	R4-3	360	Zen	open	7076	3062	
185406	R4-3	1/60	cal	clsd	7033	3004	
185525	R4-3	600/1	Zen	open	7078	3034	end 185729
185748	end R4-3	1/60	cal	clsd	7075	3044	
190003		1/60	cal	clsd	7071	3144	
190123	R4-4	300/1	Nod	clsd	7079	3064	Nod - S! caps.
190404	R4-4	300/1	Zen	open	7072	3060	
190640	R4-4	1/60	cal	clsd	7079	3079	Calibration
191215	R5	1/60	cal	clsd	7055	3064	
191346	u u	520/1	Nod	clsd	7074	3042	Stop 191702
191720	u u	1/60	cal	clsd	7066	3053	
191831	u u	600/1	Nod	clsd	7070	3078	
192337	u u	1/60	cal	clsd	7072	3092	
192500	u u	600/1	Nod	clsd	7068	3049	
192957	u u	1/60	cal	clsd	7074	3039	
19344	u u	600/1	Zen	open			
193616	u u	1/60	cal	clsd	7072	3044	
193804	u u	end	data.				

Microwave Radiometers FLIGHT LOG		Date	29/04/07	Flight	B289	log pages	2
Operator(s)	Pollard		Campaign	JAIVEX			
Departure	Ellington		Arrival	Ellington			

**System start
MARSS**

Visual pod inspection							X
Close 3 SSP circuit breakers							X
Close all MARSS circuit breakers							X
FERA on				at time	12:42		
Temperature controller initial temps	Ch16	26.7°C	Ch	26.4°C	Ch18	23.1°C	
Temperature controller set points		54°C	17	58°C	-20	40°C	
MARSS CPU on				at time	12:44		
Initial target temperatures	Hot	292.8	Cold	293.7			
Target heating							X
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***							X
Scanning on (LMD box)				at time	12:44		
Scan indication			Monitor)		Visual	X

Deimos

Close all Deimos circuit breakers							
Turn on Deimos CPU							
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***							
Start Deimos Software				at time			
Initial target temperatures	Hot		Cold				
Target heating							
Scan indication			Monitor			Visual	
Weather	Cloud		Precip				
	Surface		Pressure				
	Other						

System functionality check (after initial system warmup, approx 1 hour)

PC to DRS Time error	$t_{PC}=t_{DRS} +$	0	at time	14:04:45			
Brightness temps 'sensible'							X
Target temps	MARSS:	Hot	344.52	Cold	303.77		
	Deimos:	Hot		Cold			
Channel gains 'sensible'	Ch1 A	Ch3 A	Ch1 B	Ch3 B			
	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)			
	Ch16	Ch17	Ch18	Ch19	Ch20		
	(40-44)	(45-49)	(40-44)	(40-44)	(44-48)		
	1	33.75	37.94	39.95	40.86		

Power changeover

Headset on before start							
Listen to engine start sequence	4, 3, 2, 1.						
LMD off (3 switches, bottom to top)							
Exit Deimos Software (x)							
POWER CHANGEOVER							
LMD on (3 switches, top to bottom)	then pushbutton						
Restart Deimos Software							
System running again						at time	

Flight:

B289

KEY

- Duff Data
- Minor Problems
- OK
- Not Fitted
- Fitted, Not Operated

Thermometers

- Cabin Temperature:
- Heimann:
- Deiced Temp:
- Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

- FWVS:
- General Eastern:
- Johnson Williams:
- Nezvorov:
- Total Water Probe:

Cameras

- Downward Facing:
- Forward Facing:
- Rearward Facing:
- Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

- Cruciform GPS:
- GIN Applanix:
- INU Honeywell:
- Radar Altimeter:
- RVSM IAS:
- RVSM Static Pressure:
- XR5 GPS:

Report Created 26/06/2007
15:38:33

Misc Core

- AMTG:
- AVAPS:
- Cabin Pressure:
- Fax machine:
- Printer:
- S9 Static Pressure:
- Satcom C:
- Satcom H:
- Turb Centre-Static:
- Turb Left Right:
- Turb Up-Down:
- Turb Horizontal Chk:
- Turb Vertical Chk:
- Weather Radar:
- DLUs:**
- DLU AERACK:
- DLU BBR Lower:
- DLU BBR Upper:
- DLU Core Chem:
- DLU Core Consoles:
- DLU Port Aft:
- DLU Port Fwd:
- DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

- Lower:**
- BBR (clear) Lower:
- BBR (IR) Lower:
- BBR (red) Lower:
- Upper:**
- BBR (clear) Upper:
- BBR (IR) Upper:
- BBR (red) Upper:
- ARIES:
- DEIMOS:
- IR Camera:
- JNO2 Lower:
- JNO2 Upper:
- JO1D Lower:
- JO1D Upper:
- MARSS:
- SHIMS Lower:
- SHIMS Upper:
- SWS:
- TAFTS:

Last Updated:

Cloud Probes

- 2DC:
- 2DP:
- FFSSP:
- PCASP:
- ADA:
- CCN:
- CDP:
- CIP 100:
- CIP 25:
- CPI:
- CVI:
- SID1:
- SID2:
- Aerosol**
- CPC 3025A:
- Filters 47mm:
- Filters 90mm:
- Neph - Dry:
- Neph - Wet:
- PSAP:
- AMS:
- CPC 3025 (AMS):
- INC:
- VACC:
- CPC 3010A (CVI):

30/04/2007 21:52:42

Chemistry

- CO Aerolaser 5002:
- NOx TE42C:
- Ozone TE49C:
- Ozone TE49:
- SO2 TE43C:
- TDLAS (NIR) CH4:
- TDLAS (NIR) CO2:
- FAGE:
- Formaldehyde:
- NOxy:
- ORAC:
- PAN:
- PERCA:
- Peroxide:
- PTRMS:
- TDLAS (1C):
- WAS Bags:
- WAS Bottles:
- Misc Non-Core**
- CASI/ATM:
- LIDAR:
- LTI:
- SAW Hygrometer:

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B289

Date: 29 April 2007

Instruments

1. Not receiving SATCOM messages
2. CGPS comms failure
3. Sonde 9 – launch detect error

Aircraft

Nil

Satcom-H Calls

Not working

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) ¼ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by:

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B289:

Log	Reason
Pre-flight log	No log available
Core Chemistry	no In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems
FWVS	No log is taken for this FWVS
AMS	Log only of interest to instrument operator so no copy left with FAAM

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	31 Aug 2007	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

3 x Upward Facing Cameras
3 x Downward Facing Cameras
Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

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